

Exploiting Decision Trees to Detect Indirect Discrimination

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Abstract

Machine learning systems are increasingly present in our everyday lives, making decisions in multiple scenarios such as credit loans or advertisement displays. For this reason, there is a crescent concern regarding fairness in applying machine learning systems. Fairness is particularly relevant when such systems can affect a person’s life.

When training classification models, several approaches consider that some attributes are protected to avoid discriminatory behavior. Hence, a model should not use these attributes to make a decision. These attributes are typically sensitive features for which it is desired not to have discriminatory behavior or bias (e.g., *race* or *gender*). However, it may be possible to infer information of a protected attribute based on other non-protected attributes’ data, leading to (indirect) discriminatory behavior even without using the protected attributes.

In this work, we introduce an approach to assess whether a dataset used to train a machine learning model contains potential sources of indirect discrimination. This approach exploits the use of decision trees to identify such potential sources of discrimination. We can identify from which attributes it is possible to infer information regarding a protected attribute. These attributes are called proxy attributes. Moreover, we consider sets of proxy attributes from which it is possible to infer sensitive information when combined. If these attributes were deemed separately, no information could be inferred.

The proposed approach is applied to several datasets used in fairness-awareness studies. The experimental evaluation identifies possible reasons for indirect discriminatory behavior in the datasets. Moreover, the evaluation also considers thresholds that allow the identification of proxy attributes with a certain degree of certainty. Therefore, we can identify proxy attributes even when the dataset contains noisy data.

1 Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems, in particular Machine Learning (ML) algorithms, are currently used to make decisions in multiple scenarios, namely in sensitive environments, such as determining the risk of bank loans, displaying job-related advertisements, or making recidivism predictions (Mehrabi et al., 2021; Dressel & Farid, 2018; Berk et al., 2021; Sweeney, 2013). In these contexts, applications of ML systems are highly prone to bias. Therefore, guaranteeing fairness and non-discriminatory behavior is a crucial task.

Several ways of ensuring fairness have been proposed in the context of ML classification algorithms. For example, it is common to consider the existence of protected and non-protected attributes or features. Hence, attributes such as *gender* or *race* are protected to ensure non-discriminatory behavior. Classification models should not rely on protected attributes to make decisions.

However, discriminatory behavior may still arise from non-protected attributes. Consequently, it may be possible to infer information regarding protected attributes from the data in non-protected attributes. For instance, it may be possible to infer a person’s race based

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on the corresponding zip code, assuming that a given neighborhood is mainly inhabited by individuals of a specific race. In such a case, if an ML classification model uses the *zip code* to make a decision, although it is not using the protected attribute *race*, the resulting classification may still be racial-biased, producing discriminatory decisions. This scenario is called indirect discrimination, and the non-protected attributes, from which one can infer information about protected attributes, are called proxy attributes (Datta et al., 2017b, 2017a; Verma & Rubin, 2018; Prince & Schwarcz, 2019; Mehrabi et al., 2021; Agarwal & Mishra, 2021).

The present work aims to answer the following research questions:

- *Given a dataset, is it prone to indirect discrimination?*
In other words, can we spot possible reasons for indirect discrimination? Given a dataset, how to identify the presence of proxy attributes, *i.e.*, non-protected attributes from which it is possible to infer (some) information of a protected attribute?
- *How can we recognize proxy attributes in a dataset?*
In other words, how to identify sets of non-protected attributes that act as proxy attributes of a protected attribute?

Most of the existing approaches to identifying proxy attributes rely on the availability of domain knowledge relating non-protected with protected attributes, such as causal graphs (Kilbertus et al., 2017; Kusner et al., 2017). However, such domain knowledge is often unavailable. This is indeed the case in social contexts where fairness is very relevant.

Other approaches consider only a single non-protected attribute that acts as a proxy for a protected attribute (Datta et al., 2017b, 2017a; Yeom et al., 2018). Still, information regarding a protected attribute may be inferred when data from multiple non-protected attributes are combined, whereas no information can be inferred when considered individually. Datta et al. (2017b) consider only logical equivalence relations between proxy and protected attributes. Nevertheless, there may exist non-protected attributes from which is inferred partial information regarding a protected attribute, but the reverse does not hold. In other words, there is a logical implication but not a logical equivalence. For example, as mentioned before, it may be possible to infer a person’s race based on the corresponding zip code if a given neighborhood is mainly inhabited by individuals of a specific race, but the reverse does not hold. For this reason, one may consider the *zip code* as a proxy attribute.

The main contribution of this work is the use of random forests classifiers (Breiman, 2001), an ensemble learning method that builds several decision trees at training time, to assess whether a given dataset contains potentially discriminatory relations between non-protected and protected attributes. We exploit the use of decision trees not for predicting future data but rather to study properties of the know data used to train an ML model. Furthermore, this methodology is applied without any prior knowledge or domain information.

This paper is organized as follows. First, the background context is presented in Section 2, describing proxy attributes in Section 2.1, and then decision trees in Section 2.2. Afterwards, Section 3 introduces the proposed approach to identify proxy attributes. Finally, Section 4 presents and discusses the experimental results. Section 5 concludes the work and suggests future research directions.

2 Background

ML bias has been found in a selection of real-life applications (Mehrabi et al., 2021), such as racial-biased recidivism predictions (Dressel & Farid, 2018; Berk et al., 2021), and gender-biased job-related ads (Sweeney, 2013). Fairness in AI, dubbed fairness-aware ML,

is currently a hot topic field that aims to ensure that algorithmic systems are fair by design (Friedler, Scheidegger, & Venkatasubramanian, 2021; Ceurstemont, 2022).

2.1 Fairness and Indirect Discrimination

AI fairness is a research topic that gained increasing focus in the last few years (Adebayo et al., 2016; Friedler et al., 2019; Bird et al., 2019; Holstein et al., 2019; Chouldechova & Roth, 2020; Warner & Sloan, 2021; Aïvodji et al., 2021). Still, there has been a lack of consensus in AI fairness definitions and analysis (Verma & Rubin, 2018). Here, when considering AI fairness, we focus on machine learning classification problems.

One may summarise fairness definitions considering three categories (Verma & Rubin, 2018):

- statistical measures (Dwork et al., 2012; Hardt et al., 2016; Corbett-Davies et al., 2017; Chouldechova, 2017; Kleinberg, 2018; Berk et al., 2021);
- similarity-based measures (Dwork et al., 2012; Kusner et al., 2017; Galhotra et al., 2017);
- causal reasoning (Kusner et al., 2017; Kilbertus et al., 2017; Nabi & Shpitser, 2018).

Most fairness definitions in ML algorithms consider protected and non-protected attributes (or features), where protected attributes are sensitive features for which non-discriminatory behavior should be ensured (e.g., *race*, *religion*, or *gender*) (Ignatiev et al., 2020; Verma & Rubin, 2018; Mehrabi et al., 2021). Most algorithmic fairness work actively identifies unfairness against these protected attributes, based on the definition of fairness metrics (Dwork et al., 2012; Tramer et al., 2017; Kusner et al., 2017; Dressel & Farid, 2018).

However, observe that ignoring protected attributes in ML algorithms may not be enough to guarantee fairness (Kim, 2021), and discrimination may arise from non-protected attributes (Hajian & Domingo-Ferrer, 2012, 2013; Calmon et al., 2017; Datta et al., 2017a; Prince & Schwarcz, 2019). One approach to mitigate bias via non-protected attributes is identifying possible proxy attributes of the protected attributes. A proxy attribute is an attribute that can be used to derive or infer (some of) the value of another attribute (Datta et al., 2017a; Verma & Rubin, 2018; Prince & Schwarcz, 2019; Agarwal & Mishra, 2021). We define proxy attributes as follows:

Proxy Attributes:

Let f be a non-degenerate Boolean function, such that it returns True/1 if and only if the input variables have a specific characteristic (or values) and False/0 otherwise.

Let S be a non-empty set of non-protected attributes, and p a protected attribute.

Let X be the set of records of a dataset, described by the non-protected attributes S .

Then S is also a set of proxy attributes if there is a function f such that:

$$\exists_v \forall_{x \in X} [(f(x) = 1) \Rightarrow (p = v)]$$

Consider the example in Table 1 of a dataset with non-protected attributes NP_1 and NP_2 , and protected attribute P_1 . We say that NP_1 is a proxy attribute of P_1 since whenever NP_1 has value “a”, the protected attribute P_1 has value “x”. Note that the reverse is not true, i.e., P_1 having value “x” does not imply that NP_1 has value “a”. Moreover, note that when the value of NP_1 is not “a”, we cannot infer the value of the protected attribute P_1 . Still, we consider NP_1 a proxy attribute of P_1 due to the implication relationship mentioned before.

Now, consider the example in Table 2 with a similar dataset, having non-protected attributes NP_1 , NP_2 and NP_3 , and protected attribute P_1 . In this case, we can say that NP_1

\mathbf{NP}_1	\mathbf{NP}_2	\mathbf{P}_1
a	1	x
b	1	y
a	2	x
b	2	x
c	2	y

Table 1: Example of a dataset with non-protected attributes \mathbf{NP}_1 and \mathbf{NP}_2 , and protected attribute \mathbf{P}_1 . \mathbf{NP}_1 is a proxy attribute of \mathbf{P}_1 (when $\mathbf{NP}_1 = a$).

\mathbf{NP}_1	\mathbf{NP}_2	\mathbf{NP}_3	\mathbf{P}_1
a	1	5	x
a	2	5	y
b	1	5	y
a	1	6	x
b	2	5	x

Table 2: Example of a dataset with non-protected attributes \mathbf{NP}_1 , \mathbf{NP}_2 and \mathbf{NP}_3 , and protected attribute \mathbf{P}_1 . \mathbf{NP}_1 and \mathbf{NP}_2 combined are proxy attributes of \mathbf{P}_1 (when $\mathbf{NP}_1 = a$ AND $\mathbf{NP}_2 = 1$).

and \mathbf{NP}_2 combined are proxy attributes of the protected attribute \mathbf{P}_1 . Whenever \mathbf{NP}_1 has value “a” AND \mathbf{NP}_2 has value “1”, the protected attribute \mathbf{P}_1 has value “ x ”. Note that these attributes are proxy attributes when considered together. However, when considered separately, neither \mathbf{NP}_1 nor \mathbf{NP}_2 act as proxy attributes of \mathbf{P}_1 since no information about \mathbf{P}_1 can be inferred.

Discrimination considering proxy attributes has been studied using causal approaches (Kilbertus et al., 2017; Kusner et al., 2017). Kusner et al. (2017) introduce the definition of *counterfactual fairness* and present a framework for modeling fairness using tools from causal inference (Kusner et al., 2017). These approaches assume that the classification problem and training dataset are accompanied by a causal graph that models the domain and establishes causal relations between variables. However, causal graphs of a specific domain are often hard to find, especially in social contexts where fairness is very relevant.

Hajian et al. (2011) and Hajian and Domingo-Ferrer (2012) propose a method to detect and prevent indirect discrimination in datasets. It is considered that classification rules, i.e., rules that relate attributes with the classification class, can be Potentially Discriminatory (PD) or Potentially Non-Discriminatory (PND). A PD rule relates a protected attribute with the classification class, whereas a PND rule relates only non-protected attributes with the classification class. Therefore, a PND rule could lead to discriminatory decisions if combined with some background knowledge. To detect discrimination in PND rules, a theorem introduced by Pedreshi et al. (2008) is used to measure the degree of discrimination. Note that the authors assume that the background knowledge relating non-protected with protected attributes is available.

Previous work has also identified strong correlations between non-protected and protected attributes (Datta et al., 2017b, 2017a; Yeom et al., 2018). Datta et al. (2017a) defines the strength of a proxy given by normalized mutual information (Thomas & Joy, 2006) scores between two attributes. These scores can describe the level of association between two attributes. Then, it is assumed to exist an oracle that determines the use of a given proxy is appropriate or not. A non-protected attribute that is highly correlated with a protected attribute, and therefore identified as a potential proxy, may be considered appropriate to

Figure 1: Example of a Decision Tree for the dataset represented in Table 1.

use in an ML model by a human expert in the domain.

2.2 Decision Trees

In this work, we consider using decision tree (DT) classifiers to extract information from the DT learned when such a model is trained using the non-protected attributes as training data and a protected attribute as a classification target. A DT (Breiman et al., 2017; Loh, 2014) is a directed acyclic graph, with a root node. A DT node can be either a decision node or a leaf node. A decision node represents a decision point where an attribute is used, with some condition, to partition, or split, the dataset. Each decision node has two children nodes: one in case the condition of the decision node is True; the other in case it is False. A leaf node is a node without children and has a class associated. Each node of a DT has an associated depth, representing the distance from the root node.

Figure 1 illustrates an example of a DT for the dataset represented in Table 1 considering P_1 as the classification target. Circular nodes represent decision nodes, and rectangular nodes represent leaf nodes.

Considering a DT trained with a given dataset, we can associate with each node the number of samples, or records, of the dataset that reached that node. Moreover, we can measure the quality of a split in a decision node. In this work, we consider the Gini impurity measure (Breiman et al., 2017; Daniya, Geetha, & Kumar, 2020). Consider that there are K classes and that $p(i)$ is the probability of a record having class $i \in K$, knowing the record reached a given decision node n . Then, the Gini impurity of node n , denoted $G(n)$, is given by:

$$G(n) = \sum_{i \in K} p(i)(1 - p(i)) \tag{1}$$

The Gini impurity level of a given node is between 0 and 0.5, where a value of 0 means that all the records used as training data that reached that node have the same classification value.

For example, consider the DT represented in Figure 1 and the corresponding dataset in Table 1. Three records reach the node with the label “ $NP_2 > 1$ ” (second, fourth, and fifth records in Table 1), which are the records that failed the previous condition of $NP_1 == \text{“a”}$. Then, the Gini value for that node, considering the mentioned records and Equation 1, is given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
g &= \sum_{i \in K} p(i)(1 - p(i)) \\
&= p(x)(1 - p(x)) + p(y)(1 - p(y)) \\
&= \frac{1}{3} \times \left(1 - \frac{1}{3}\right) + \frac{2}{3} \times \left(1 - \frac{2}{3}\right) \\
&= \frac{4}{9} \approx 0.444
\end{aligned}$$

3 Identifying Potential Proxy Attributes

This work introduces an approach to effectively identify the presence of potential proxy attributes given a dataset intended to train an ML classification model and the corresponding protected attributes. This approach works as a pre-processing step to be applied to ML datasets to assess whether the dataset contains potential sources of indirect discrimination *before* it is used to train an ML model. Note that we exploit DT models not to predict future data but rather to identify properties (proxy attributes) present in the know data. We consider that there is no prior knowledge available (such as a causal graph) for characterizing the domain of the analyzed dataset.

Consider that a dataset has one or more protected attributes, i.e., attributes for which it is desirable to have non-discriminatory behavior. In this context, proxy attributes are non-protected attributes from which it is possible to infer all or part of some information of a protected attribute.

Recall that this work aims to use ML classification algorithms, in particular DT classifiers, to assess whether from non-protected attributes it is possible to determine values of protected attributes. To do so, we generate a version of the dataset to be analyzed that contains only the non-protected attributes, as shown in Figure 2. Then, we consider each protected attribute as the classification target, and we train an ML model. Intuitively, if the model trained has a high accuracy score, then it is possible to infer, with high accuracy, information regarding the protected attribute from the non-protected attributes. Hence, the dataset may contain proxy attributes. Moreover, an ML model trained using the original dataset may lead to indirect discrimination due to proxy attributes.

We have selected DT classifiers for their simplicity and explainability. In practice, we use Random Forests (RF) classifiers (Breiman, 2001), an ensemble learning method that builds several DTs at training time, to assess whether a given dataset contains potentially discriminatory relations between non-protected and protected attributes.

In our implementation, the RF classifier generates 100 trees with a given maximum depth. The algorithm analyzes each one of the generated DT, and the presence of nodes with an impurity level of zero is identified. A node with an impurity level of zero, associated with a path in the DT, represents the possibility of uniquely determining the value of the classification target without uncertainty, considering the dataset provided. Furthermore, the path to the identified node represents an explanation for the assignment of the protected attribute considered as the classification target based on the non-protected attributes of the dataset. Hence, the non-protected attributes contained in such an explanation (path in a DT) may be considered proxy attributes of the given protected attribute. Figure 2 illustrates the process of identifying potential proxy attributes, starting with the generation of versions of the dataset containing only the non-protected attributes. Then, for each protected attribute, an RF classifier is trained, having the protected attribute as the classification target. Finally, all the DTs generated by the classifier are analyzed, and information regarding the

Figure 2: Proposed approach to identify proxy attributes of protected attributes.

Algorithm 1 Identification of potential proxy attributes

Input: Dataset D (*non-protected attributes*); Classification target C (*protected attribute*); Maximum depth d .

Parameters: Impurity level threshold $t \in [0; 0.5]$; Minimum percentage of records $r \in [0; 1]$.

Output: Set of sets of potential proxy attributes.

```

1: Res  $\leftarrow \emptyset$ 
2: RandomForestClassifier( $D, C, d$ ) {Train classifier.}
3: for all decision trees generated do
4:   for all nodes in decision tree do
5:      $n_i \leftarrow$  current node impurity level
6:      $n_r \leftarrow$  percentage of records that reached the current node
7:      $n_p \leftarrow$  path to current node
8:     if  $n_i \leq t \wedge n_r \geq r$  then
9:       Res  $\leftarrow$  Res  $\cup \{n_p\}$ 
10:    end if
11:  end for
12: end for
13: return Res
  
```

potential proxy attributes is retrieved by looking at nodes with zero impurity. This approach is represented by Algorithm 1 that receives as input: a dataset D , containing only non-protected attributes; a classification target C , a protected attribute for which we are identifying potential proxy attributes; and a maximum depth d for the DTs.

One can apply this procedure iteratively, considering an increasing maximum depth d limit for the DTs in Algorithm 1. With such an approach, it is possible to identify nodes with an impurity level of zero at different depths, representing explanations of different lengths. Additionally, this process can identify sets of non-protected attributes that can infer information regarding a protected attribute when combined under certain conditions. In contrast, if the non-protected attributes are considered individually, we cannot infer the same information.

Furthermore, a threshold for the impurity level of the nodes of the DTs can be considered. Considering a small threshold for the impurity level allows the identification of potential

proxy attributes with a high degree of certainty. For example, consider a path in a DT for which dozens or hundreds of dataset records have the same target classification. Consider also that for this path, only one record does not have the same classification value as all other. Hence, we may want to consider that we are in the presence of a set of proxy attributes, even if it is not with 100% certainty. Thus, assuming a small threshold for the impurity levels allows us to identify such cases of the existence of proxy attributes as well. As a result, Algorithm 1 can be parameterized with an impurity level threshold $t \in [0; 0.5]$.

Another aspect to be taken into account is the percentage of records. When analyzing a DT searching for nodes with an impurity level below a given threshold, one may consider the percentage of records being considered at each node. For example, if a node with an impurity level of zero is found, but only one record of the dataset (with hundreds of thousands of records) reaches that specific node, the path to that node may not represent a significant reason for indirect discrimination. Therefore, we consider that Algorithm 1 can be further parameterized by defining a minimum percentage of records $r \in [0; 1]$. This percentage establishes the number of records a node must have for the path to that node to be a potential set of proxy attributes with higher confidence.

The implementation of the proposed approach to identify sets of proxy attributes is publicly available at <https://github.com/FilipeGouveia/Riga>.

4 Experimental Results

To evaluate our work, we applied the proposed method of identifying potential proxy attributes to publicly available datasets and used it in the context of ML fairness studies (Le Quy et al., 2022).

The experimental evaluation comprehends two distinct evaluation settings. The first one concerns the identification of proxy attributes. The second one examines the impact of proxy attributes in classification.

4.1 Datasets

The experimental results in this work refer to publicly available financial, criminological, healthcare, education, and social datasets. These datasets have been used in the past in studies regarding fairness and bias in ML (Le Quy et al., 2022).

The *Adult* dataset (Kohavi et al., 1996) is a well known dataset used in fairness-aware classification studies (Zemel et al., 2013; Chierichetti et al., 2017; Krasanakis et al., 2018; Bellamy et al., 2019; d’Aloisio et al., 2022; Sikdar et al., 2022). This dataset contains census information, and its classification task is to predict whether a person’s annual income exceeds 50 000 US dollars. It contains 45 222 records, and 13 attributes. Three of the attributes are considered protected: *sex*, *age*, and *race*.

The *Bank-marketing* dataset (Moro et al., 2014; Krasanakis et al., 2018; Galhotra et al., 2021; Abbasi et al., 2021) contains information regarding direct marketing campaigns of a Portuguese banking institution. The target classification of this dataset is to predict whether a client will make a deposit subscription. It contains 45 211 records, and 16 attributes. Two of the attributes are considered protected: *age*, and *marital* status.

The *COMPAS* dataset (Angwin et al., 2016) is well known and used for crime recidivism risk prediction (Chouldechova, 2017; Corbett-Davies et al., 2017; Krasanakis et al., 2018; Slack et al., 2020; Diana et al., 2021). We considered 6 907 records, and 22 attributes. Two of the attributes are considered protected: *sex*, and *race*. We also considered a version of this dataset containing only records where the individual was arrested within 30 days of the date of a crime as suggested in (Le Quy et al., 2022).

Dataset	#Records	#Attr.	#Prot.	#N-Prot.	#N-Prot. (One-hot)
Adult	45222	13	3	10	95
Bank-marketing	45211	16	2	14	47
COMPAS	6907	22	2	20	27
COMPAS (30 days)	6623	22	2	20	27
Credit Card	30000	23	3	20	20
Diabetes	98053	44	1	43	2347
Diabetes (readmitted)	45715	44	1	43	1980
German Credit	1000	21	3	18	58
KDD	284556	37	2	35	364
Lawschool	20798	16	2	14	41
OULAD	31482	10	1	9	46
Ricci	118	5	1	4	5
Students (Math.)	395	32	2	30	55
Students (Port.)	649	32	2	30	55

Table 3: Number of records, attributes (#Attr.), protected attributes (#Prot.), non-protected attributes (#N-Prot.), and non-protected attributes after using one-hot encoding (#N-Prot.(One-hot)) of each dataset.

The *Credit Card* dataset (Yeh & hui Lien, 2009; Berk et al., 2017; Esmaeili et al., 2020) contains data of clients’ default payments and it has been used for default payment prediction. This dataset contains 30 000 records, and 23 attributes. Three of the attributes are considered protected: *education*, *marriage*, and *sex*.

The *Diabetes* dataset (Strack et al., 2014; Chierichetti et al., 2017; Backurs et al., 2019) contains clinical information and the goal is to predict whether a patient will be readmitted within 30 days. We considered 98 053 records, and 44 attributes. The attribute *gender* is the only protected attribute. We also considered a version of this dataset where a patient is readmitted within 30 days or more than 30 days. The records where the patient is not readmitted were excluded from the dataset as suggested in (Le Quy et al., 2022).

The *German Credit* dataset (Dua & Graff, 2017; Pedreshi et al., 2008; Calders et al., 2009; Friedler et al., 2019) contains samples of bank account holders and is used for credit risk assessment prediction. This dataset contains 1,000 records, and 21 attributes. Here, we consider three protected attributes: *age*, *age_cat* (age category), and *foreign_worker* (whether the individual is a foreign worker or not).

The *KDD Census-Income* dataset (Dua & Graff, 2017; Ristanoski et al., 2013; Iosifidis & Ntoutsis, 2019, 2020) contains data from population surveys from 1994 to 1995 in the US. The classification target is to predict whether a person receives more than 50 000 US dollars, the same as the *Adult* dataset. The dataset contains 284 556 records, the biggest dataset considered, and 37 attributes. Two of the attributes are considered protected: *race*, and *sex*.

The *Lawschool* dataset (Wightman, 1998; Kusner et al., 2017; Berk et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2020; Chzhen et al., 2020) contains law school admission records across 163 law schools in the US in 1991. The goal is to predict if a candidate will pass the bar exam. This dataset contains 20 798 records, and 16 attributes. Two of the attributes are considered protected: *gender*, and *race*.

The *OULAD* (Open University Learning Analytics) dataset (Kuzilek et al., 2017; Riazzy & Simbeck, 2019) contains information about students and their activities in virtual learning environments. The prediction task is to predict the success of a student. The dataset contains

31 482 records, and 10 attributes, where only *gender* is considered a protected attribute.

The *Ricci* dataset (Supreme Court of the United States, 2009; Friedler et al., 2019; Ignatiev et al., 2020) contains information regarding promotion decisions within a fire department and was generated by the Ricci v. DeStefano case of the Supreme Court of the United States (Supreme Court of the United States, 2009). This dataset contains only 118 records, and 5 attributes, where only *race* is considered a protected attribute.

The *Students* dataset (Cortez & Silva, 2008) contains data regarding students in two Portuguese high schools. This dataset considers two different curricular units: Portuguese (Port.) and Mathematics (Math.) The dataset contains 395 records of Math. students and 649 of Port. students. There are 32 attributes, two of which are considered protected: *sex*, and *age*.

Regarding the encoding, we applied a one-hot encoding (Harris & Harris, 2010) to each dataset’s categorical non-protected attributes, transforming them into multiple binary attributes with the same information. Such transformation does not introduce any bias (Biswas & Rajan, 2021). Table 3 indicates the number of (non-protected) attributes that resulted from this transformation.

More detailed information regarding the datasets and corresponding attributes are described by Le Quy et al. (2022). A summary of each dataset characteristic is shown in Table 3.

4.2 Evaluation I: Identification of Proxy Attributes

To evaluate our work, we have run the proposed approach over the non-protected attributes of each dataset to identify potential proxy attributes for each of the corresponding protected attributes. Here, we only considered protected attributes with categorical values. We do not use the protected attribute *age* as a classification target since it has a range of values and, therefore, is unsuitable for this approach. This results from the nature of the DT classifiers for which a discrete small set of classification values is desirable.

As we are looking for small explanations for potential indirect discrimination reasons, i.e., a small set of attributes that act as a proxy, we consider an iteratively increasing maximum depth from 1 to 10 for the DTs. Note that higher values can be considered for the maximum depth. However, explaining potential indirect discriminatory behavior based on many (e.g., 20) attributes may not be desirable.

Initially, we evaluated the presented approach considering an impurity level threshold of zero. Table 4 shows the nodes with minimum depth found, with an impurity level of zero, considering the ten iterations. We could find an explanation for potential indirect discrimination with a size of 4 or less for all datasets and corresponding target protected attributes. In other words, we could discover nodes with zero impurity at a depth of 4 or less. Hence, the algorithm can infer information regarding the corresponding protected attribute based on 4 non-protected attributes or even fewer. The minimum depth of a node with an impurity level of zero was 4 only for the *education* attribute of the Credit Card dataset, whereas for the other datasets was less than 4.

However, when analyzing the results, we verified that some datasets contained errors affecting the identification of potential sources of indirect discrimination. For example, considering the Adult dataset and potential proxy attributes for the attribute *sex*, the minimum depth of a node with an impurity level of zero was 2. However, looking at the corresponding DT illustrated in Figure 3, we noticed that having the value “Husband” in attribute *relationship* was not enough to unequivocally determine the value of attribute *sex* as it would be expected. Further analysis of the dataset showed that there is only one record with *relationship* with value “Husband” that does not have value “Male” as *sex*. We can assume that

Dataset	Target	Min. depth
Adult	sex	2
Adult	race	1
Bank-marketing	marital	2
COMPAS	race	2
COMPAS	sex	2
COMPAS (30 days)	race	2
COMPAS (30 days)	sex	2
Credit Card	education	4
Credit Card	marriage	3
Credit Card	sex	3
Diabetes	gender	1
Diabetes (readmitted)	gender	1
German Credit	age_cat	2
German Credit	foreign_worker	1
KDD	race	2
KDD	sex	2
Lawschool	gender	2
Lawschool	race	2
OULAD	gender	2
Ricci	race	1
Students (Math.)	sex	1
Students (Port.)	sex	2

Table 4: Minimum node depth found with zero impurity per dataset, per protected attribute used as classification target.

Figure 3: Example of a Decision Tree for the Adult dataset when searching for proxy attributes for the protected attribute *sex* (used as classification target).

such a record has an error, and we would like to consider that the attribute *relationship* can be a proxy attribute of the attribute *sex*. Therefore, we should consider a threshold for the impurity level (e.g., 0.01).

We conducted further experiments, performing the same ten iterations with an increased maximum depth from 1 to 10, considering an impurity threshold of 0.01. The overall results

Dataset	Target	Max. rec. %
Adult	sex	41.43
Adult	race	0.64
Bank-marketing	marital	0.61
COMPAS	race	0.91
COMPAS	sex	1.94
COMPAS (30 days)	race	0.97
COMPAS (30 days)	sex	1.99
Credit Card	education	0.13
Credit Card	marriage	0.38
Credit Card	sex	0.26
Diabetes	gender	0.34
Diabetes (readmitted)	gender	0.17
German Credit	age_cat	14.20
German Credit	foreign_worker	55.90
KDD	race	1.14
KDD	sex	1.19
Lawschool	gender	0.18
Lawschool	race	1.37
OULAD	gender	0.39
Ricci	race	12.71
Students (Math.)	sex	10.38
Students (Port.)	sex	6.93

Table 5: Maximum records (Max. rec.) found, in percentage, that reached a node with impurity level lower than 0.01 per dataset, per protected attribute used as classification target.

did not change from the results shown in Table 4. However, as expected, we could find a node at depth 1 with an impurity level below 0.01 when searching for proxy attributes of the attribute *sex* in the Adult dataset.

Table 5 shows the maximum percentage of records of each dataset that reached a node with an impurity level below 0.01. In five instances, we found a node with an impurity level below 0.01 that represented more than 10% of the records of the dataset. Therefore, in some cases, we were able to find sets of non-protected attributes that, when combined under some conditions, can determine the value of a protected attribute, matching a considerable percentage of the corresponding dataset.

The analysis of the proxy attributes identified leads to the following remarks:

- The *native-country* attribute of the Adult dataset can be considered a proxy attribute of *race*, as expected.
- The value of the *sex* attribute of the Adult dataset can determine the *relationship* attribute when it has the value “Husband” or “Wife”.
- Most proxies found for the protected attribute *sex* in the Adult dataset included a combination of one or more of the following attributes: *relationship*, *marital_status*, *occupation*, *education-num*, *hours-per-week*, and *workclass*. This finding follows known information regarding the relationship between attributes in the Adult dataset (Le Quy et al., 2022).

- In the COMPAS dataset, individuals with a *v_score_text* with value “High” and a juvenile felony count (*juv_fel_count*) greater than 2 are “Male”.
- The attribute *diag_2* (secondary diagnosis) in the Diabetes dataset having code “648” can be used to infer the gender of the individual as “Female”.
- In contrast, in the Diabetes dataset, if the value of *diag_1* is “600”, then the individuals are “Male”.
- The attributes *num_dependents* and *housing* of the German Credit dataset, when combined, can determine the value of the protected *age_cat* attribute.
- The *combine* attribute (combined score) of the Ricci dataset is a proxy attribute of *race*.
- The *sex* of the individuals in the Students dataset can be inferred through attributes *walc* (weekend alcohol consumption) and *studytime*. In particular, when *walc* and *studytime* have both high values, the individuals are male.

4.3 Evaluation II: Impact of Proxy Attributes in Classification

To further analyze the proxy attributes found with the proposed approach, we measure the impact of a record belonging to a proxy for the classification target in the original datasets. For that, we considered the odds ratio measure and the impact ratio measure (Pedreschi et al., 2009; Szumilas, 2010; Sharif Rohani, 2021).

Let Y be the classification target, where $y^+ \in Y$ represents a positive outcome, and $y^- \in Y$ represents a negative outcome. Let S^0 denote the records that satisfy the conditions of a given proxy, and S^1 denote the records that do not meet the requirements of the same proxy.

The **Odds Ratio** (OR) measures the effect that being exposed to a particular group (proxy) has on the outcome. The OR can be defined as:

$$OR = \frac{p(y^+|S^0)p(y^-|S^1)}{p(y^+|S^1)p(y^-|S^0)} \quad (2)$$

In the context of this work, the OR measure can be interpreted as follows:

- $OR = 1$: Belonging to the proxy does not affect the odds of the outcome.
- $OR > 1$: Belonging to the proxy causes higher odds of a positive outcome.
- $OR < 1$: Belonging to the proxy causes lower odds of a positive outcome.

The **Impact Ratio** (IR) measures the ratio of positive outcomes for a particular group (proxy) over the general group. The closer this ratio is to one, the less biased the proxy is. The IR can be defined as:

$$IR = \frac{p(y^+|S^0)}{p(y^+|S^1)} \quad (3)$$

The IR can be interpreted as follows:

- $IR = 0$: Maximum discrimination for the proxy group.

Figure 4: Classification target distribution of the Adult dataset.

Figure 5: Classification target distribution of the Adult dataset considering the records that have *relationship* = “Husband”.

- $IR = 1$: No discrimination.
- $IR = +\infty$: Reverse discrimination for the proxy group.

Considering the Adult dataset, the proxy attribute found (*relationship* == “Husband”) for the protected attribute *sex*, describes 18 665 records with *sex*=“Male” and 1 record with *sex*=“Female”, covering 41.28% of the dataset. Considering S^0 as the records that satisfy the proxy condition and y^+ as having a positive outcome of *target*=“> 50K”, we have that $OR = 7.396$ and $IR = 4.481$. These values mean that satisfying the proxy condition, which is a proxy for the protected attribute *sex* (having value “Male”), increases the odds of a positive outcome (or leads to positive discrimination). These results can be observed in Figure 4 and Figure 5, where it is represented the distribution of the target classification values for the whole dataset and for the records that satisfy the proxy condition, respectively.

More detailed results can be seen at <https://github.com/FilipeGouveia/Riga>.

5 Conclusion and Future Research Directions

This work presents an approach that exploits the use of decision trees to identify proxy attributes in a dataset intended to train machine learning classification models. The proxy attributes are identified without any background knowledge of the domain of the corresponding dataset. Here, we identify proxy attributes from which it is possible to infer information about a given protected attribute, even if it is only partial information. Moreover, the presented approach identifies sets of proxy attributes that are only proxy attributes if considered combined. Hence, if these attributes are considered individually, they are not recognized as proxy attributes. The implementation of the presented approach is available at <https://github.com/FilipeGouveia/Riga>.

The proposed approach was applied to several publicly available datasets used in fairness-aware studies (Le Quy et al., 2022). We identify potential proxy attributes for all the protected attributes of the corresponding datasets. This finding is relevant and enlightening in the context of fairness.

However, in some contexts, a more careful analysis may be required. For example, the following situations may represent false positives and so deserve attention:

- When the identified proxy attributes represent some statistical phenomenon of the dataset’s domain;
- When only a tiny percentage of a dataset falls under the corresponding proxy attributes identified conditions;
- When the identified proxy attributes are just evidencing the unbalance of the dataset regarding some protected attribute.

In such cases, a domain expert must evaluate whether one should consider the identified proxy attributes.

Future work should focus on research for approaches to minimize the mentioned cases of false positives.

The presented approach only identifies some proxy attributes (or set of proxy attributes). Therefore, we intend to pursue different methods to identify proxy attributes that, for example, can identify every (set of) proxy attributes or consider optimization criteria, such as identifying the smallest size proxy possible.

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